

Towards High-Fidelity and Trustworthy Digital Twins for Fault Diagnosis in Grid Connected Inverters

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Abstract—Automating the task of fault detection and diagnosis is essential for reducing the operational and maintenance costs of power electronic converters. Hence, this paper introduces an online optimization methodology for digital twins to diagnose multiple faults in grid connected inverters. In addition to enhancing accuracy, we channelize our efforts towards reducing computational complexity in parameter configuration under a limited set of training data. To address cybersecurity vulnerabilities during the training phase of our digital twin, we perform *data sanitization* with the aid of a quantitative association rule mining technique. For classification performance assessment, various fault cases in a virtual synchronous generator are considered to demonstrate the efficacy of our approach. Our research outcomes reveal increased accuracy and fidelity levels achieved by our digital-twin design, paving the way for reliable and trustworthy decision-making under anomalous conditions.

Index Terms—digital twin, grid connected inverters, fault diagnosis, hyperparameter tuning, quantitative association rule mining

I. INTRODUCTION

In the course of the ongoing transformation of traditional power systems, grid-forming converters have been identified as key components ensuring the seamless integration of renewable energy sources (e.g., photovoltaic power plants and wind energy generators) and storage batteries. By actively controlling their frequency and voltage outputs, grid-forming converters contribute to grid stability and guarantee efficient

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energy management. Nevertheless, such power electronic components are inherently susceptible to various types of faulty behavior, which can be attributed either to the malfunction of their hardware elements or defective operation of the power grid.

Although many efforts have been carried out on grid-forming virtual synchronous generators (VSGs) to expedite stability under different grid conditions, their operation under faults or large signal disturbances still remains a challenge [1]. Grid-forming converters are able to sustain only a significantly smaller percentage of over-current (typically around 20%) compared to synchronous generators, which can handle fault currents up to seven times their nominal current [2]. Hence, the detection of such abnormal operating conditions of grid-forming converters becomes imperative to enable a widespread penetration of converters and ensure reliable grid operation [3]. As the network infrastructure of power systems keeps expanding, it is also essential to accurately identify faults under varying grid parameter uncertainties.

The installation of devices such as active power filters (APF) or the development of new control strategies for grid connected inverters with the capability to ride through such contingencies has gathered significant interest from both the research community and industry. However, APFs have limited power storage capacity to mitigate long-lasting power fluctuations and voltage dips in medium and high voltage levels. Furthermore, such solutions involve the deployment of additional devices, thereby increasing the overall cost. The primary drawback with grid-forming converters is that for sudden disturbances or faults with high dv/dt , df/dt , the thresholds defined for voltage/frequency changes in the power generation control and protection systems often lead to unnecessary load shedding and, at times, tripping of generation [4]. This issue varies from a demographic point of view, as grid codes and grid strength differ significantly across countries. Recently, grid-forming converters have gained popularity to overcome aforementioned drawbacks [5], [6]. However, the response to short circuits and other contingencies remains a concern, as these can easily lead to loss of synchronization.

A. Related work

The design of resilient methodologies to tackle such anomalies has recently attracted remarkable research attention due to growing unreliability and natural disasters leading to power interruptions. Traditional anomaly detection methods in the

literature rely on classic strategies such as switching patterns and voltage observers [7], [8] or frequency analysis [9]. Despite the effectiveness of these approaches, they are highly application-dependent and primarily focused on modulation techniques. On the other hand, the emergence of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) techniques and their applicability in power electronics holds the promise of enhanced detection accuracy and cognitive reasoning [10].

Recent studies applying ML models for fault diagnosis in power electronics demonstrate benefits, particularly in terms of computational time and the ability to deal with system parametrization [11]–[13]. In [14], a data-driven mechanism is employed to distinguish between various physical anomalies in power electronic systems. Additionally, notable anomaly detection solutions have been proposed in [15], [16], which categorize fault conditions and cyber-attacks by fusing model-based and advanced physics-informed ML methods.

Digital twins have recently gained popularity as an emerging technology for monitoring long-term and short-term anomalies in power electronic converters [17], [18]. By capitalizing on their ability to provide virtual representations of physical assets, digital twins are increasingly used for condition monitoring, fault detection, predictive diagnostics, and maintenance guidelines for reduced downtime. Their prototypical hallmark lies in their capability to leverage AI/ML tools and data analytics to transform monitoring information into actionable insights. An essential aspect of digital twins resides in the quantification of system attributes, which paves the way for data-driven methodologies tailored for improved operation and informed decision-making [19]. In particular, fault identification and classification of abnormal measurements are data-empowered tasks that would benefit from digital-twin deployments.

Although digital-twin adoption in power electronics appears capable of revolutionizing their operation, several challenges remain. These challenges are primarily related to their resilient and scalable design, high-fidelity modularity, and timely synchronization between digital and physical counterparts. Currently, digital twins for power electronics are primarily designed for dynamic and long time-series problems, such as condition and health monitoring [20], control [21], and design [22], which rely on extensive historical data of degradation profiles or dynamic operating conditions. While this approach guarantees good performance, achieving high accuracy levels depends significantly on the quantity of data. However, an effective methodology for designing digital twins for critical applications, such as fault and anomaly diagnosis with limited data, is still lacking. Additionally, data availability is not the only concern; there is also a need for robust and explainable mechanisms that ensure fast decision-making with provable guarantees.

As already mentioned, the overall efficiency of digital twins is largely governed by the quantity as well as the quality of imported monitoring data [23]. High-quality measurement streams fed into the digital twin provide behavioral insights into its real-world counterpart. Conversely, a digital twin can

be ill-governed when perturbed or corrupted measurements are intentionally introduced as cyberattacks, requiring optimization. Such cases, often termed *data poisoning*, depend on the magnitude of adversarial data injected into the existing dataset. Furthermore, the convenience of remote-control capabilities, coupled with the inherent security vulnerabilities of the underlying communication infrastructure, expands the attack surface of digital-twin deployments, giving rise to finely targeted and stealthy cyber-attacks [24], [25]. Security threats span a wide range of risks, ranging from data confidentiality and integrity (e.g., adversarial manipulations) to information availability (e.g., denial-of-service) and privacy leakage [26].

B. Contribution

To address such challenges, this paper introduces a novel digital-twin framework for VSG-controlled grid-forming converters, specifically tailored for fault diagnosis and data poisoning detection. Our data-driven methodology aims to: (i) accurately determine abnormal operating conditions pertaining to various fault classes under limited training data¹, and (ii) detect malicious instances in raw measured data that target the training phase of the digital twin. Unlike existing digital-twin approaches that rely on opaque algorithms, our proposed framework not only enhances the resilience of its physical counterpart but also offers instructive insights by formalizing *high confidence* over its decisions. Compared to our prior work [27], we extend our methodology in the following directions:

- We elaborate on the foundational principles and operational mechanisms of our digital-twin implementation for fault diagnosis. Our objective is to elucidate the capability of our framework to discover causal relationships between sensor variables and fault diagnosis outcomes in a computationally efficient manner.
- We incorporate an effective algorithm for detecting data poisoning. This addresses scenarios where the training phase of the digital twin is deliberately compromised by adversaries aiming to disrupt the learning process. Our objective is to accurately identify data manipulations in the form of carefully crafted malicious samples, intended to influence decision-making in the fault classification task.

C. Organization

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II provides an overview of the proposed digital-twin framework for VSG-controlled grid-forming converters. Section III elaborates on the methodological aspects of our fault diagnosis approach, including explainability insights for decision-making. Section IV introduces our algorithm for detecting poisoning attacks during the training phase of the digital twin. Results pertaining to the performance of our

¹In our study, we have considered a limited raw dataset of 18,460 samples collected with 50Hz frequency on a digital twin. The initial and final spikes due to the starting and shutting down of the grid connected inverter have been removed.

Fig. 1: Optimized digital-twin framework for a VSG-controlled grid-forming converter.

framework for fault diagnosis and attack detection are presented in Section V. Section VI is reserved for the conclusions and discussion of the path forward.

II. PROPOSED DIGITAL-TWIN FRAMEWORK

To demonstrate the proposed data-driven framework, we employ the following dynamic model of the VSG-controlled grid-forming converters [28], as illustrated in Fig. 1:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u} \quad (1)$$

where, $\mathbf{x} = [v_g, i_o, \omega, v_{dc}, P_e, Q_e]$, $\mathbf{u} = [P_{ref}, Q_{ref}]$ represent the state and control input vectors, respectively. The anomalies considered are: (i) line-to-line faults, (ii) sensor faults, (iii) single-phase voltage sag, and (iv) three-phase faults. Each fault type has significantly distinct characteristics and magnitude. To validate the practicality and carry out the design of the digital twin, we collect fault data at a sampling frequency of 5 kHz from the experimental prototype shown in Fig. 2. Two cabinets with three-phase 7.5 kW DC-AC converters are employed, where converter B is utilized as a VSG. The faults outlined as classes in Fig. 1 are introduced in the transmission line connected directly to a programmable PQ load.

Fig. 2: Experimental prototype of the system topology shown in Fig. 1. Data is collected prior to every fault class defined in the table within Fig. 1.

The key parameters used in the proposed setup are presented next. A three-phase grid-forming converter (Converter B) of 7.5 kVA in Fig. 2 is connected to the programmable PQ load via an interfacing LC filter. It is controlled as per the control diagram in Fig. 1 with the system and control parameters, given by: $L_f = 1.5$ mH, $C_v = 10$ μ F, $V_n = 230$ V, $\omega_r = 314.15$

Fig. 3: Comparative performance of the VSG equipped with a digital twin trained with and without poisoned data. Although the regression curve does not suggest a big difference, an unbalanced waveform can be observed in the presence of data poisoning.

rad/s, $J = 0.4$ sec, $D_p = 0.05$ p.u., $k_p = 5.4$, $k_e = 16.8$, $k_q = 7.8$, $f_{sw} = 10$ kHz.

Our goal is to design a single-input single-output (SISO) surrogate model [29] of the considered system, trained using a dataset obtained under different operating conditions, including both steady-state as well as transient fault scenarios. The idea is to diagnose system faults with a higher precision using only electrical measurements, which thereby justifies the selection criteria behind the SISO model. It is worth noting that, even under steady-state conditions, it is essential to attribute the loading levels, power factor, and other variables as additional labels, which can otherwise lead to diagnosis errors. In this work, fault diagnosis is treated as a multi-class classification problem. As shown in Fig. 1, the digital twin acquires measurement streams from the control platform to feed data-driven classification models that perform fault identification. Once a fault type is determined, appropriate protection action needs to be taken to ensure maximum system reliability and uptime.

Data acquisition for digital-twin deployment is inevitably

susceptible to cybersecurity breaches by adversaries aiming to contaminate the original data used for training the classification model. Such data poisoning attacks can shift the decision boundaries of classifiers, leading to erroneous fault diagnosis outcomes. To illustrate this research gap, consider a simple example where one of the inputs in \mathbf{x} in (1), i.e., v_g , is subjected to random poisoned values in \mathbf{Z} , which are bounded within $[-0.05, 0.05]$ p.u. It should be noted that the non-zero values are randomly allocated in \mathbf{Z} , with the number of non-zero values considered for this test case being only $\text{supp}(\mathbf{Z}) = 5000$. As shown in Fig. 3, although the prediction accuracy is quite close (≈ 0.9999) for both cases, their performance differs significantly. Compared to the balanced voltage v_{abc} without data poisoning, the performance is drastically affected by the unbalancing among the three-phase voltages due to the poisoned data. Moreover, when a voltage sag disturbance of 50% is introduced at $t = 0.2$ sec, the voltage unbalancing factor increases.

Thus, to ensure the trustworthiness of our digital-twin deployment against such threats, we employ a detection algorithm based on a quantitative association rule mining technique. Training data sanitization can be achieved by removing samples from the training set that would lead to misclassification errors.

III. DESIGN PRINCIPLES FOR FAULT DIAGNOSIS

One of the key design challenges for the operational efficiency of digital twins is the appropriate selection of the parameters used to control the behavior of the learning model/algorithm. This process, often referred to as *hyperparameter tuning*, is crucial for the successful generalization of fault detection and classification in grid-forming converters. Hyperparameter tuning involves defining a search space where each dimension corresponds to a hyperparameter, and each point represents a model configuration. The goal of this optimization procedure is to determine a vector that results in the best performance of the fault classification model after learning. In particular, the optimal configuration needs to minimize the misclassification error on the training dataset.

An important concern in hyperparameter configuration is the associated computational cost. Properly configuring hyperparameters (e.g., regularization weights, learning rate, number of hidden layers) requires the execution of consecutive experiments, each corresponding to a single combination of hyperparameter values, where the model is trained end-to-end. Addressing this computational complexity is essential for rapid decision-making on various fault cases. To this end, we propose a computationally efficient methodology, where hyperparameter tuning is performed with formal guarantees that uncertainty can be reduced over time. Our objective is to narrow down the hyperparameter search space by exploiting regions that are already known to be promising, thus avoiding redundant and costly evaluations that may otherwise render hyperparameter configuration a computationally burdensome process.

Fig. 4: Building blocks of our digital-twin framework tailored for fault diagnosis.

The building blocks of our optimization framework are illustrated in Fig. 4. We provide the details in the following subsections.

A. Model selection

In the quest for the most appropriate model for fault diagnosis in grid-forming converters, we consider several *out-of-the-box* open-source platforms capable of providing customized versions of ML algorithms. Our focus is on tools that produce high-quality models suitable for direct deployment in production environments, leveraging scheduling, parallelism, and early-stopping in the ML workflow. Explainability capabilities are also important, as uncertainties in decision-making may restrict the deployment of these models for power electronic converters.

In this context, we consider the following methods for the identification of the most suitable model for fault diagnosis in grid-forming converters:

- **Automatic Machine Learning (AutoML):** The AutoML implementation by H2O [30] offers a highly scalable supervised learning algorithm that automates the training process of a large set of candidate models and stacked ensembles within a single function. In this work, we consider AutoML as an option for automated model selection for multi-class classification. For each model, AutoML identifies the most important hyperparameters, defines acceptable ranges/bounds for those parameters, and utilizes random search for hyperparameter tuning.
- **Traditional statistical models:** Given the plethora of fault classifier algorithms available, we consider conventional ML methods, such as logistic regression, to perform model approximation. This approach contrasts with the AutoML option, which incorporates complex ensemble methods.
- **Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM):** In model approximation using GBM, an ensemble formation strategy is employed where new models are sequentially added to the ensemble to enhance the accuracy of the target variable estimation. The flexibility in model design renders GBMs highly customizable to any particular data-driven task while offering several hyperparameter tuning options. In this work, we focus on LightGBM, a gradient boosting decision tree (GBDT) algorithm that accelerates the train-

Fig. 5: Methodology for hyperparameter tuning of our digital-twin framework applied for the diagnosis of faults in power electronic converters.

ing process of conventional GBDT while maintaining equivalent accuracy. Besides improving computational efficiency and scalability, LightGBM offers an intuitive application programming interface to incorporate customized training and validation loss functions [31].

- **Deep Learning (DL) approaches:** We investigate the feasibility of two novel DL architectures for the multi-class classification task: TabTransformer [32] and Tabnet [33]. The TabTransformer has been recently proposed to bridge the performance gap between multi-layer perceptron (MLP) models and GBDT algorithms. In addition to improving interpretability compared to MLPs, the self-attention layers in the TabTransformer architecture generate robust data representations (i.e., embeddings) for categorical variables to achieve higher accuracy. Such contextual embeddings are also resilient against both missing and noisy data features. Conversely, Tabnet combines the feature selection property of tree-based algorithms with the ability of deep neural networks to fit complex functions, to select only the relevant features at each decision step of the training process.

It is noted that datasets pertaining to fault diagnosis are typically imbalanced, meaning that the number of samples for some fault classes is much less than the data samples corresponding to normal operation. Therefore, in both LightGBM and DL approaches, we incorporate a customized implementation of the focal loss function [34], tailored for multi-class classification of imbalanced tabular datasets.

B. Model parameter optimization

Although the built-in functionality of the aforementioned methods offers satisfactory classification performance, additional gains can be attained by applying *online* model optimization using a Bayesian approach. Our methodology, illustrated in Fig. 5, defines a prior belief over possible objective functions and sequentially refines the model as data is observed (i.e., function evaluations) via Bayesian posterior updating. Hyperparameter tuning can thus become more

computationally efficient. For our experiments, we consider a relatively small dataset of 104,001 set-points to expedite the learning capabilities of our digital twin. We use 80% of the data for training, 10% for validation, and 10% for testing. For model testing, we combine the validation and testing datasets, as neither was used for training the models.

For experiment orchestration, we use a Ray Tune cluster [35] comprising the Bayesian parameter search algorithm for optimizing algorithm hyperparameters and the asynchronous successive halving algorithm (ASHA) as a pruning method to facilitate early stopping of poorly performing trials [36]. Our distributed implementation in Ray Tune allows the search for hyperparameter combinations to be conducted across several machines in parallel. Experiment tracking, model versioning, and deployment are performed with the aid of the Weights and Biases platform under an academic license [37]. Our optimization framework is publicly available on the FIREMAN project GitHub repository [38].

The iterative workflow for hyperparameter tuning is illustrated in Fig. 6a. The automated ML pipeline preprocesses the grid-forming converter dataset and incrementally drops features (i.e., measurements) to improve classification performance. More specifically:

- Step 1: Model parameters are tuned using Ray Tune;
- Step 2: Performance metrics of the best trained model are stored, and features are ranked according to their importance or the outcomes of SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) method [39];
- Step 3: The feature associated with the worst-achieved performance is dropped from the dataset.

The iterative process of parameter tuning and feature dropping is repeated until the model performance is no longer improving. We consider this as an equivalent technique to principled *early stopping*, a widely used regularization technique for parameter and model tuning. Instead of terminating model training when the performance no longer improves, we gradually eliminate features and retrain/re-tune the model until further performance gains are minimal.

There are four potential outcomes of a classification model: (i) correctly detected faults or True Positives (TP); (ii) correctly detected normal behaviors or True Negatives (TN); (iii) incorrect identification of a normal behavior as a fault or False Positives (FP); (iv) incorrect identification of a fault as a normal behavior or False Negatives (FN). Classification performance is evaluated using commonly used metrics, i.e., *Accuracy*, *Precision*, *Recall*, and *F1 score*, defined as

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{TP} + \text{TN}}{\text{TP} + \text{TN} + \text{FP} + \text{FN}}, \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FP}}, \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FN}}, \quad (4)$$

$$\text{F1} = \frac{2 \cdot \text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}, \quad (5)$$

(a) The iterative process of parameter tuning and feature dropping for a model. Features are dropped incrementally until the evaluated performance of the model is no longer improved.

(b) Hyperparameter tuning of an MLP network conducted in a *step-wise* manner. The F1 score is considered as the performance assessment metric (y-axis). The DL model parameters under consideration for tuning include hidden layers, learning rate scheduler, optimizer, and training batch size. The color-filled areas under the curves depict the performance range of parameter values within each tuning group, spanning from the minimum to the maximum values.

Fig. 6: Hyperparameter tuning process.

respectively. The accuracy indicates the ratio of all correct detections to the overall number of input samples. Precision and recall values capture the impact of FP and FN rates, respectively. The F1 score represents the harmonic mean between precision and recall metrics. These metrics collectively provide insights into the robustness and effectiveness of the fault diagnosis.

Hyperparameter tuning for the DL approaches considered in Section III-A is inherently more complex than in conventional ML models. DL models involve a multitude of parameters including numerical settings, such as batch size and learning rate, selection of activation and loss functions, optimization algorithms, and the architecture of hidden layers, to name a few. Finding the best configuration for these parameters in such a high-dimensional space is thus a non-trivial challenge. To manage such complexity effectively, we adopt a *define-by-run* approach as introduced in [40]. This method dynamically constructs the search spaces for the model hyperparameters, adjusting them iteratively based on historical performance evaluations. Specifically, we implement a *step-wise* algorithm in LightGBM tuner, where each parameter is *independently sampled* to iteratively narrow down the search space. The value

of a single parameter is independently determined without considering any relationship between parameters. This iterative process leverages past evaluations to build a probabilistic model, guiding the selection of subsequent hyperparameter sets to evaluate. In summary:

- Step 1: The value search space for each parameter is defined;
- Step 2: The order of parameters is set, and sample parameters are drawn;
- Step 3: The set of parameters yielding the greatest expected improvement are returned.

Fig. 6b illustrates the hyperparameter tuning process for an MLP network using the step-wise algorithmic approach. The most commonly used MLP parameters (hidden layers, learning rate scheduler, optimizer, and training batch size) are divided into groups that are tuned sequentially. When a specific group undergoes tuning, all *subsequent* groups are set to default/initial values, and all *preceding* groups are set to the values obtained after their respective tuning processes. It should be underlined that the resulting parameter value set is influenced by the order in which tuning occurs and may not necessarily yield the optimal parameter combination. Nevertheless, this approach is deemed a computationally efficient alternative to exhaustive parameter grid search, as it focuses on narrowing down the hyperparameter space specific to the group being tuned.

C. Output explanation

In multi-class classification problems, models typically estimate the likelihood of each class outcome based on a given set of inputs. SHAP is a widely used explainability technique that leverages cooperative game theory to quantify the impact of each feature on the model's classification decisions [39]. To determine feature attribution, SHAP evaluates all possible combinations of input features to determine the significance of each feature towards the overall classification outcome.

To shed light on the LightGBM model predictions, Fig. 7 depicts the SHAP decision plots for instances of normal behavior and each type of fault. Each plot reveals the extent to which each feature (y-axis) contributes to the prediction of each fault type and normal behavior (as defined in Fig. 1). Additionally, the plots include the final prediction probability for each class. Summary feature impact plots for the entire testing dataset are illustrated in Fig. 8. By incorporating such explainable insights into our methodology, we are able to handle complex multidimensional scenarios, where the root cause behind the model's predictions seems to be elusive.

IV. DETECTION OF POISONING ATTACKS ON TRAINING DATA

The consideration of AI/ML-based digital twins for fault diagnosis in power electronic converters is a double-edged sword. AI/ML models, albeit offering increased accuracy and fidelity levels, expand the attack surface, giving rise to new threat vectors of escalating severity and complexity. Notably, data poisoning attacks aim to manipulate the training data of a digital twin to degrade classification performance at test time.

Fig. 7: SHAP decision plots for LightGBM model predictions when applied for fault classification in grid-forming converters. SHAP values reveal individual feature contributions and differentiate among different classes of faults and normal behavior. The red curve represents the most favorable decision taken by the model, while the blue curves represent the less favorable decisions. The vertical axis displays the input features, and the horizontal axes show the probabilities of reaching to correct decisions. For each instance in the data (i.e. row), the contribution from each input feature towards the model's prediction varies depending on the values of the features for that particular instance.

To detect poisoning attacks that induce misclassification errors in our digital-twin framework, we resort to a rule-based learner, coined as the *quantitative association rule mining algorithm* (QARMA) [41]. QARMA aims at extracting efficiently² all quantitative association rules that satisfy a user-defined minimum threshold of *support* and *confidence* on a training set. The support of a rule denotes the fraction of instances where the rule is satisfied across the entire dataset, while the confidence indicates the accuracy of the rule on training instances where the antecedents are satisfied. Higher support suggests that the rule is applicable to a larger portion of the dataset, while confidence indicates how often the rule has been found to be true.

Given a dataset comprised of instances of data having values for (not necessarily all of) the so-called attributes of the dataset, QARMA returns rules of the following forms

$$I_1 \in [l_1, h_1] \wedge \dots \wedge I_n \in [l_n, h_n] \rightarrow T = v, \quad (6)$$

$$I_1 \in [l_1, h_1] \wedge \dots \wedge I_n \in [l_n, h_n] \rightarrow T \geq v, \quad (7)$$

$$I_1 \in [l_1, h_1] \wedge \dots \wedge I_n \in [l_n, h_n] \rightarrow T \leq v. \quad (8)$$

where $I_i, i \in A$, and T denote quantitative attributes in the dataset. Each rule specifies restrictions on the values of the

²QARMA leverages parallel computing and exhibits linear (or even super-linear) scaling performance with the number of available threads in a processing unit [41].

attributes in its antecedent conditions using half- or fully-closed intervals. The consequent condition specifies that the value of the target attribute either assumes an exact value or lies within a half-closed interval. Such rules can rarely hold with 100% accuracy, thus QARMA only seeks rules that hold with support and confidence above certain thresholds in the training dataset. Hence, each rule r in the extracted ruleset \mathcal{R} is guaranteed to hold on the dataset with support s and confidence c exceeding the user-specified thresholds. Moreover, each rule r is guaranteed to be non-redundant, or equivalently there is no other rule $r' \in \mathcal{R}$ providing more information (i.e., no r' holds with the same or better s and c whenever r holds, thus specifying a stricter inequality).

Although QARMA has already been successfully applied for predictive maintenance and fault classification tasks in industrial settings [42], [43], its potential for detecting poisoning attacks is being explored for the first time in this study. Specifically, we consider a relatively generic realization of poisoning attack on the training dataset of our digital-twin framework in the form of *training label manipulation*. In this case, an adversary contaminates the original data used for training the classification model by flipping labels [44]. Such a label-flip poisoning strategy aims at mislabeling a subset of training samples, e.g., by changing the labels of faulty instances to indicate normal behavior instead. This

Fig. 8: SHAP value impact on LightGBM model output applied for fault classification in grid-forming converters. Summary plots provide an overview of feature impact on predictions for different classes of faults and normal behavior.

Algorithm 1 Quantitative association rule mining for detecting poisoning attacks

Extract all rules that hold with a given support s and confidence c threshold in the training dataset, and store them in ruleset \mathcal{R} .

Initialize $S = \emptyset$.

For each instance x of the training data **do**:

Find the set R'_x of all rules $r \in \mathcal{R}$ whose antecedent conditions are satisfied by the values of the attributes of x but whose consequent specifies a different class label from that of x .

If the cardinality of the set R'_x is greater than a user-defined threshold $f \geq 0$ **then**

Add instance x to S .

End For

Return the set S .

manipulation compromises the accuracy of the classifiers, as the characteristic patterns indicating the occurrence of a fault are not effectively learned. In addition to reduced classification accuracy, adverse effects may also include decreased learning rate, increased proportions of abnormal instances that remain misclassified, and increased variability in detection metrics.

Our main intuition is that the extracted rules from QARMA can be made to have very small supports on the dataset yet maintain high confidence levels. Each rule's antecedents define a hyper-parallelepiped in a space with as many dimensions as the number of antecedent conditions in the rule. A high-confidence rule can be envisioned as a volume within which we can assign a high probability for the target class being equal to the consequent of the rule, especially for instances in the relative interior of such volumes (as opposed to those belonging to the enclosing surface of the volumes). We would expect this belief to be reinforced if multiple such rules hold for a particular instance in the training set that, however, provide wrong classifications for the instance. Algorithm 1 outlines the operational steps followed in QARMA for detecting malicious data instances within a training dataset.

The strictness of QARMA is primarily governed by the parameter f , and indirectly by the parameters s, c . The higher the values of all three parameters, the more challenging it becomes for any instance x to be included in the result set S of the algorithm. Albeit QARMA seems to be well-suited to detect instances whose labels have been manipulated, its utility can extend to scenarios involving adversarial attacks where attribute values are intentionally missing from the training dataset. Even in cases where the training data suffers

Fig. 9: Performance of VSG controlled grid-forming converter under two types of disturbance: (a) multi-label – Three-phase voltage sag introduced at $t = 0.2$ sec and three-phase fault at $t = 0.28$ sec; (b) single-label – Phase A voltage sag of 0.5 pu is introduced at $t = 0.2$ sec.

from incomplete attribute values (but retains the class label), QARMA can still be used to infer instances where both the class label and some attribute values have been maliciously withheld by an adversary.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we evaluate the efficacy of our digital-twin framework for fault diagnosis and detection of poisoning attacks. Our experiments are performed using a dataset comprising four different types of faults and the normal behavior of a VSG.

A. Dataset description

To ascertain the robust design of the digital twin, the states \mathbf{x} and inputs \mathbf{u} corresponding to every fault instance, are concatenated into a global dataset $\mathbb{D}_{104001 \times 8}$. This dataset was obtained from a 2-level grid-tied converter of 7.5 kVA (as depicted in Fig. 2). Training, validation, and testing have been carried out using 80%, 10%, and 10% of the entire dataset, respectively.

B. Fault diagnosis

The performance of our digital twin for fault diagnosis in VSG-controlled grid-forming converters is evaluated under two instances of disturbances; in the first case, two consecutive faults occur in adjacent timestamps (i.e., at $t = 0.2$ and $t = 0.28$ sec), while in the second case, a single-class fault is considered at $t = 0.2$ sec, as shown in Fig. 9. Since the training data is primarily composed of recorded faults and anomaly behavior, it is worth emphasizing that the global dataset for fault diagnosis will quite often be small due to the limited occurrences of faults compared to normal operation cases. In such critical cases with limited data settings, system behavior might be compromised due to the digital-twin operation, as their dynamic response becomes highly similar. This further aggravates the challenge, as the detection time is stringent. Overall, this mandates a highly precise and fast classification ability with the proposed digital twin for fault diagnosis in power electronic converters.

To evaluate the feasibility of our framework for fault diagnosis, we first assess the model classification performance using the four model identification methods discussed in Section III-A. Specifically, we evaluate the classification

TABLE I: Model comparison in terms of classification performance

Model	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Weighted AUC
Stacked ensembles (AutoML)	0.92	0.91	0.91	0.9985
Logistic regression	0.53	0.64	0.53	0.6856
LightGBM (log-loss)	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.9986
LightGBM (focal loss)	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.9989
TabTransformer	0.26	0.28	0.24	0.4656
Tabnet	0.37	0.32	0.29	0.4967

performance for the optimal AutoML model (i.e., the model exhibiting the lowest mean per class error in the default leaderboard) and the conventional logistic regression model. Next, hyperparameter tuning on LightGBM and DL models is carried out, following the methodology outlined in Section III-B. Table I summarizes the performance achieved by the aforementioned fault diagnosis models, evaluated over a subset of the entire dataset. Higher precision corresponds to lower FP rates, while higher recall outcomes indicate lower FN rates. A higher F1 score indicates better detection performance. The weighted area under the curve (AUC) is also computed to summarize the overall diagnostic ability of the classification models across all threshold values while accounting for the imbalanced class distributions in our dataset. It can be observed that a fine-tuned LightGBM model with a customized multi-class focal loss function offers superior performance compared to its classifier counterparts.

To elucidate the hyperparameter configuration process, the parallel coordinate plots in Fig. 10a reveal the impact of various parameter combinations on the fine-tuning of LightGBM (focal loss), identified as the best-performing model in Table I. In particular, the rightmost column depicts the achieved accuracy with LightGBM, while wavy lines associate these outcomes with all corresponding hyperparameter values represented by vertical lines. Each wavy line represents a single experiment and is colored according to the outcome (e.g., darker tones indicate lower accuracy, while brighter tones indicate higher accuracy). Such illustration allows us to identify correlations in hyperparameter searches. The effect of different parameter configurations on the focal loss function and accuracy of the LightGBM model are illustrated in Figs. 10b and 10c, respectively. It should be noted that our framework employs early stopping for model configurations that exhibit higher focal loss and lower accuracy, thereby

Fig. 10: LightGBM training procedure. The parallel coordinates plot in Fig. 10a associates various combinations of algorithm hyperparameters with the achieved accuracy levels of the trained models. Figs. 10b and 10c depict the training process optimization over elapsed time steps (horizontal axis). Utilizing the applied pruning method, models with low-performing parameter combinations (i.e., those exhibiting high focal loss and low accuracy) are stopped early by the ASHA scheduler to conserve computational resources for the high-performing parameter configurations.

conserving computational resources for high-performing models. By eliminating poorly performing parameter combinations while retaining those that perform well, we train models with higher certainty in decision-making.

Considering the entire dataset, the multi-class classification performance of the LightGBM model with the optimal hyperparameter configuration is summarized in Table II. For the evaluation, standard classification metrics (i.e., accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score) are used, considering the combined validation and test dataset predictions from the model that exhibited the optimal performance on the training dataset. The classification report also includes: (i) the macro-averaged scores, calculated using the arithmetic mean of all individual per-class scores, and (ii) the weighted-averaged scores, calculated by taking the mean of all per-class scores while accounting for the support for each class. Each weight is computed as the proportion of each class's support relative to the sum of all support values.

C. Data poisoning detection

For the realization of the poisoning attack on the training dataset of our digital twin, we performed label flipping on the first 10 measurements associated with a single-class fault. The labels of these abnormal instances, which constitute 0.5% of the total faulty data, were manipulated to indicate the normal behavior class, thereby causing misclassification of the model on the test samples. The remaining training dataset, comprising

TABLE II: LightGBM classification outcomes using various metrics

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Normal behavior	0.99	0.99	0.99
Line-to-line fault	0.88	0.72	0.79
Three-phase sensor fault	0.99	1.0	0.99
Single-phase voltage sag	0.99	0.99	0.99
Three-phase grid fault	0.93	0.75	0.83
Macro average	0.96	0.89	0.92
Weighted average	0.99	0.99	0.99
Accuracy	0.99		

normal behavior and faulty instances, remained unaltered. It is noted that such a poisoning attack strategy is sample-generic (i.e., indiscriminate) since any fraction of the training data can be targeted by the adversary.

For the detection of data poisoning with QARMA, we extracted all rules from the training dataset with a minimum support of 0.1% and a minimum confidence of 80%. With the specification of a sufficiently low threshold for support, we aimed to capture the rarity of the poisoning attack frequency in the training dataset. At the same time, by setting a sufficiently high confidence threshold for the derived rules, QARMA is capable of generating a (possibly large) collection of rules that trigger infrequently but, when they do, they detect the poisoning attack with high likelihood.

TABLE III: TP and FP rates for data poisoning attack identification using QARMA in our digital-twin framework

f	$s_{\min} = 0.001$								$s_{\min} = 0.002$				$s_{\min} = 0.005$			
	$c_{\min} = 0.8$				$c_{\min} = 0.85$				$c_{\min} = 0.82$				$c_{\min} = 0.8$			
	10	50	90	150	10	13	14	15	10	20	30	40	10	15	20	50
TP rate	0.9	0.9	0.8	0.5	0.9	0.8	0.6	0.5	1	0.9	0.8	0.5	0.8	0.8	0.7	0.4
FP rate	0.61	0.335	0.229	0.151	0.424	0.385	0.376	0.366	0.5	0.4	0.331	0.28	0.5	0.44	0.387	0.238

The results of applying Algorithm 1 are shown in Table III for various parameter configurations. In this case, the TP rate is defined as the rate at which manipulated data instances by an adversary are correctly identified. On the other hand, the FP rate represents the rate at which unaltered data instances are incorrectly identified as manipulated. It can be observed that an increased TP rate of QARMA comes with the inadvertent cost of an elevated FP rate. In other words, achieving high attack detection accuracy with QARMA requires the removal of samples leading to FPs from the original training dataset. For example, as depicted in Fig. 11, we can detect 90% of all manipulated samples if we tolerate retaining only 66.5% (for $f=50$) of our original training dataset. Alternatively, we can detect 80% of all manipulated samples if we are willing to remove 22.9% (for $f=90$) of the original training dataset.

Reducing the dataset size as a means to enhance protection from poisoning attacks may impact the fault detection performance of our digital-twin framework. Fig. 12 depicts the LightGBM classification performance for fault diagnosis after removing the samples that lead to FPs in poisoning attack detection with QARMA (TP rate=0.8, FP rate=0.229). Interestingly, it can be observed that classification metrics improve (i.e., blue vs red bars). This can be attributed to the fact that the training samples selected by QARMA for removal tend to lead the classifier to erroneous outcomes, i.e., a mismatch of training labels. This is corroborated by the poor classification performance achieved by these samples (i.e., green bars). Thus, as a favorable side effect of the QARMA dataset sanitization strategy for attack detection, fault classification is shown to become more accurate. On the other hand, classification improvement may come at the expense of reduced generalization performance, since LightGBM may lose the ability to respond to unknown samples.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The ongoing transition from conventional power systems to power electronics-dominated grids has increased the demand for grid-forming converters to facilitate reliable operating conditions. However, fault diagnosis with insufficient fault condition measurements and varying grid parameter uncertainties becomes challenging and may threaten synchronization with the grid. To address this issue, we propose a framework to optimize the operation of digital twins employed for fault diagnosis of grid connected inverters by applying online model optimization using a Bayesian approach. Besides enhancing accuracy, our methodology renders parameter learning more computationally efficient while conforming to rapid decision-

Fig. 11: Tradeoff between TP and FP rates achieved with QARMA for $s_{\min} = 0.001$ and $c_{\min} = 0.8$.

Fig. 12: LightGBM classification performance after removing samples leading to FPs in poisoning attack detection with QARMA (for TP rate=0.8 and FP rate=0.229).

making for various fault scenarios. In addition, our framework is designed to be robust against data poisoning attacks, which aim to deliberately influence fault diagnosis outcomes.

Improved fault diagnosis and insights gained from digital twins can be leveraged to optimize the design of new inverters or enhance existing ones, leading to more efficient and reliable grid-connected systems. Our research advances the field of digital twins for grid connected inverters by enabling the seamless integration of the proposed framework with the artificial intelligence of things (AIoT) paradigm at the edge, using the Kubernetes orchestration platform³. This would facilitate smarter grid management and control. Our methodology also allows for interpreting the outputs of digital twins and translat-

³<https://kubernetes.io/>

ing them into actionable insights for fault diagnosis, especially when dealing with multiple possible fault scenarios. Finally, it is noted that, under unforeseen or evolving grid conditions, the proposed digital-twin framework incorporates two complementary mechanisms: (i) calibrated probability thresholds in the LightGBM classifier for unknown-class detection, and (ii) QARMA-based rule violation monitoring to identify previously unseen fault behaviors and novel poisoning attacks, accordingly. Together, these components enable the digital twin to detect deviations from known operating regimes and maintain diagnostic reliability under evolving grid dynamics.

In the path forward, we plan to leverage the potential of our framework in operating with limited training data and explore its feasibility as an *edge digital twin* for power electronics with the aid of TinyML solutions. Notably, our digital-twin pipeline achieves sub-millisecond inference performance by coupling a lightweight LightGBM ensemble (1–500 μ s per sample [45]) with efficient QARMA rule evaluation (10–100 μ s per sample [46]). This ensures real-time operation within typical edge-hardware resource limits, supporting the practical realization of low-latency, high-fidelity edge digital twins for grid-connected inverter diagnostics. In such an experimental setup, the emerging federated learning paradigm will also be explored, by integrating GBMs and DL models with the federated averaging algorithm [47] to diffuse intelligence across multiple embedded devices. This integration is expected to tackle use cases involving the training of a shared prediction model among multiple power electrical circuits. Finally, we will direct our efforts towards online power system stability assessment, and overcome the burden in terms of computational modeling and analysis.

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